

BOOK REPAIR

M. Usmanov

Head of the Treasury of Resources
International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7249008>

From time immemorial, the book has been valued in all nations as a source of virtue leading to goodness. Any good work related to the book was also considered honorable. First of all, writing a book and reading it is spiritual maturity, which always has good consequences.

The word "book" appears in more than 200 verses of the Holy Qur'an, and the verses indicating its meaning are also mentioned many times.

The word "kitab" is Arabic, and in the dictionary it means "to collect", "to collect". Arabs, when all the sons and daughters and grandchildren belonging to a large family gather in the father's yard, they say "Takattaba banu fulan", that is, "The descendants of so-and-so are gathered." It is also used to type something in a row.

Its meaning in istilah means a book of several pages in our native language.

The book is the source of culture and enlightenment, development, the knowledge contained in it is the food for the perfection of the mind, the peace of the heart and soul, as well as the guide that leads humanity to goodness.

In the world of books, there are manuscript copies that are an invaluable treasure, the first source, the root of our modern development. Before these books were found in our funds, they had a very hard time, natural and man-made disasters seriously damaged most of them.

Our hardworking forefathers spent so much time to create this priceless treasure, the "Sahih al-Jame'" collection of Imam Bukhari is the result of fifteen years of work. And Ibn Hajar Asqalani spent thirty years of his life to write a commentary on "Sahih al-Jame'".

Today, as the heirs of the great scholars, are we properly preserving these treasures, and most importantly, are we learning the knowledge that leads to the happiness of this world and the hereafter? Today, we cannot find solutions to the increasingly complex problems if all efforts are not mobilized for science and enlightenment.

Manuscript books are distinguished from printed books by a certain mysterious magic. When you read them, every line, every letter will make you feel how impartial our great ancestors were, who used all their possibilities for future generations. As Yusuf Khos Hajib said:

The pen of the wise does not finish, The world of music will remain dark.

Despite the great importance of some manuscripts for the development of mankind, the names of their authors were not recorded. Looking for the author and reading the places where the author is written, you will notice the honest lines "In the name of a servant in need of God's mercy".

The age of the oldest manuscript books, which have become such a priceless value, is more than 1400 years old. In this regard, many of them need to be renovated. Although there are few owners of the rare profession known as "book doctors" in our country today. They serve as a bridge between the past and the future in this field. Today, the revival of this industry is gaining momentum in the West and the East. In particular, several laboratories are operating in this field in independent Uzbekistan. Ancient manuscripts, wills and documents, as well as genealogies and genealogies are stored at the Institute of Oriental Studies Manuscripts named after Abu Raykhan Beruni, Center of Islamic Civilization of Uzbekistan, International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan, Central State Archive and many historical museums of our country. Today, along with the study of this priceless heritage, among them, books that have been damaged for various reasons are being restored as much as possible.

If we look at the history of the creation of a manuscript book, we can witness the participation of several people, including the paper maker, the scientist who wrote the book, that is, the author of the first manuscript copy, and then calligraphers, scribes, sheets (to kurrosas) to reproduce it in several numbers.) sewing and binding workers participated.

Three main methods of repair are developing:

- mechanical method using special modern equipment;
- through special equipment using heat energy.
- through manual labor;

Mechanical repair is mainly used in the restoration of lithographic books. In this method, using modern technologies, various powders obtained from natural materials such as tree barks are used. A suitable color is selected from the powders depending on the color of the paper, and the amount of powder is determined depending on the thickness or thinness of the paper and a solution is prepared in water. The damaged pages of the book are separated and placed in special containers. The bottom part of the special containers consists of very small holes, and when necessary, the mixed water inside is drained through these very small holes, as a result, powder lumps are filled in the torn spaces in the sheets, and they come to a complete state.

The second method is thermal repair, which mainly repairs lithographic books. The modern special equipment has wide and long strips, on the surface of which the damaged pages of the book are sorted and a special adhesive paper is covered over them. The belt takes the sheets to a high-temperature special device (furnace), as a result of which the damaged sheets are restored by means of glue and paper. In the process of repair by these two methods above, the paper of the book may be damaged to a certain extent, especially rare manuscripts may cause serious damage to the unique paper and writings in the books, so it is not recommended to repair the manuscript books by these methods.

The third method, i.e. manual repair, is the most ancient method, and is the most suitable method, especially for rare manuscript books. In this method, the original copy of the manuscript is not changed or negatively affected. According to it, all the pages of the manuscript are first numbered and separated separately, and the damaged, torn or burned pages, as well as those damaged by biological pests, are placed on the repair table. Paper equal to the size of a book page, close to the quality of the same page, is prepared, or the clean paper of books whose text has been completely destroyed, and the blank pages of which are at the edges of the text, is used. Then a new paper with a torn page of the book is glued with natural glue. Then the excess parts of the new paper are removed using a special knife, the edges are smoothed with fine sandpaper, and as a result, a single page is created. Missing texts on the page are filled in with notes if they exist in other copies.

The second method is thermal repair, which mainly repairs lithographic books. The modern special equipment has wide and long strips, on the surface of which the damaged pages of the book are sorted and a special adhesive paper is covered over them. The belt takes the sheets to a high-temperature special device (furnace), as a result of which the damaged sheets are restored by means of glue and paper. In the process of repair by these two methods above, the paper of the book may be damaged to a certain extent, especially rare manuscripts may cause serious damage to the unique paper and writings in the books, so it is not recommended to repair the manuscript books by these methods.

The third method, i.e. manual repair, is the most ancient method, and is the most suitable method, especially for rare manuscript books. In this method, the original copy of the manuscript is not changed or negatively affected. According to it, all the pages of the manuscript are first numbered and separated

separately, and the damaged, torn or burned pages, as well as those damaged by biological pests, are placed on the repair table. Paper equal to the size of a book page, close to the quality of the same page, is prepared, or the clean paper of books whose text has been completely destroyed, and the blank pages of which are at the edges of the text, is used. Then a new paper with a torn page of the book is glued with natural glue. Then the excess parts of the new paper are removed using a special knife, the edges are smoothed with fine sandpaper, and as a result, a single page is created. Missing texts on the page are filled in with notes if they exist in other copies.

Representatives of this field should be loving, faithful, very attentive to the heritage of our ancestors, and also very patient. Around this ancient manuscript standing on a lighted glass table, a specialist in white robes holding repair equipment such as surgeon's tools in his hands, a surgeon standing over a patient waiting for salvation, should be taken into consideration no less than a doctor, and the manuscripts are silent patient needs light treatment.

Sorting pages, restoring, collating, binding - these four repair processes are carried out depending on the level of damage of the book. If the pages are torn out of the seams, they are sorted "Tad'im", if a piece is torn and lost, "Tarmim" is restored, if the pages are torn, "Tajmi" is collected and stitched, and "Tasbit" is performed for strong binding. Each field has its pros and cons:

- 1) when the restorer works on ancient manuscripts, the dust and germs that have been accumulating for many years, as well as chemical harmful substances and gases during chemical processing, have a negative effect on his respiratory organs;
- 2) diseases similar to eczema may occur on the skin of the repairer's hands or face;
- 3) negative impact on eyesight during long-term work on a specially lit desktop;
- 4) sitting still for a long time can cause spine and back pain;
- 5) the repair of rare resources imposes its own responsibility, risks, which has a negative effect on the nerves and psyche.

Such negative effects are worth it in the face of good results such as prolonging the life of manuscripts and serving for the happiness of the world and the hereafter, and dedicated experts in this field are proud of their honorable task of preserving the priceless heritage of their ancestors and leaving it intact for generations and spend their precious lives.

References:

1. Доктор Бассом Доғистоний. Ал-манҳаж ан-назарий ли даврати ат-тармим

2. Ал-мадату ал-илмия ли даврати ат-тахқиқ ал-хамиса
3. www.almajidcenter.org

